

Resource availability for e-MGO adoption in maritime transport: A case study in the Port of Barcelona

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ABSTRACT

Power-to-Liquid processes have the potential to decarbonize maritime transport by producing carbon-neutral electro-fuels. One example of a potential implementation of this process is the combined technology of co-electrolysis of carbon dioxide and water, along with Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis. Given the promising prospects of producing electro-fuels to achieve net-zero objectives by 2050, a critical question that arises is whether sufficient resources are available to replace the current demand for fossil marine gas oil (MGO). This study evaluates the requirements and availability of resources necessary for producing marine electro-fuel using the MGO demand at the Port of Barcelona as a case study. The results indicate that current supplies of renewable energy and biogenic CO₂ are insufficient to fully replace the total fossil MGO demand. However, by 2050, it is expected that these resource limitations will be overcome, considering the current official projections for the growth of renewable electricity and the biogas industry. The deployment of renewable electricity generation and the rollout of biomethane industrial network as biogenic carbon source is found to be essential for the viability of the future substitution of fossil MGO with its electro-fuel equivalent.

1. Introduction

Maritime transport currently contributes 13.5 % of the total transport emissions in the European Union (EU). As part of the EU's Fit for 55 packages, the FuelEU Maritime initiative aims to progressively reduce the intensity of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, targeting an 80 % reduction by 2050, while also boosting demand for low-carbon fuels [1]. Meanwhile, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set a goal of achieving net zero emissions for the maritime sector by 2050, with an interim target of reducing absolute emissions by 20 % by 2030 and 70 % by 2040. Additionally, technologies, fuels, or energy sources with zero or near-zero GHG emissions must account for at least 5 % of the energy used in international maritime transport by 2030 [2]. The FuelEU maritime initiative will incentivize the uptake of renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO) [1]. These synthetic fuels are produced using hydrogen derived from renewable energy (RE) (excluding biomass) and CO₂ or N₂. In the maritime sector, RFNBOs include hydrogen, hydrocarbons (such as methane, gasoline, diesel, and others),

ammonia (NH₃) and oxygenated fuels (methanol, ethanol, dimethyl ether (DME), oxymethylene ether (OME), and ethyl *tert*-butyl ether (ETBE)) [3].

The International Transport Forum acknowledges that multiple strategies exist for reducing carbon emissions, such as utilizing alternative fuels (including sustainable biofuels, hydrogen, ammonia and methanol) and electrifying ships [4]. Additionally, many techno-economical studies have been carried out for alternative fuels in the maritime sector. Mukherjee et al. [5] and Korberg et al. [6] proposed methanol, ammonia, and dimethyl ether (DME) as affordable fuels in the long term. While each of these fuels has its own benefits, e-MGO's primary advantage lies in its ability to blend with conventional MGO. This allows for a gradual replacement of fossil fuels without requiring changes to existing ship equipment or infrastructure. In terms of technical properties, e-MGO presents a higher volumetric energy density (37 MJ/L), a significantly higher cetane number (<35), a lower autoignition temperature (210 °C), and a flash point that meets safety standards (>60 °C) [7]. Given these attributes, e-MGO is considered an attractive

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alternative in the medium to long term.

From an environmental perspective, e-MGO is one of the cleanest fuel options available, emitting only 9 g CO₂/kWh, which is 645 g CO₂/kWh less than conventional MGO [8]. Since e-MGO is produced through CO₂ utilization, it aligns with the FuelEU Maritime initiative, which promotes the implementation of RFNBOs. Furthermore, e-MGO is an attractive choice due to its minimal feedstock emissions, as it does not emit methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), black carbon (BC), or sulfur oxides (SO_x) [9].

The Power-to-X (PtX) concept refers to the conversion of electricity, particularly from renewable sources, into various products for future use [10]. When these products are liquid fuels, the process is specifically termed Power-to-Liquid (PtL). These fuels, collectively known as “electrofuels” or “e-fuels,” are produced from captured CO₂ or nitrogen (N₂) separated from the air, in combination with hydrogen generated via water electrolysis [11]. Given its promising potential as a key solution in advancing the clean energy transition toward a circular economy and sustainability, the environmental impact of PtL technology is a critical consideration. The extent of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions depends on the origin of the CO₂ feedstock and the electricity used in the process [12,13].

Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis (FTS) is a chemical/catalytic process that allows an efficient production of synthetic fuels, such as e-MGO, using syngas as a feedstock [14]. Syngas consists of a mixture of H₂ and CO in different ratios, which can be obtained by different methods. Conventional methods for producing syngas include steam reforming, dry reforming, partial oxidation, and gasification of hydrocarbons from fossil sources. Novel technologies encompass electrolysis, plasma, and microchannel reactors [15,16]. Syngas can also be derived from renewable sources by biomass gasification (bio-syngas) [17], water splitting via electrolysis or thermolysis, and the reverse water–gas shift (RWGS) reaction [18]. A highly promising CO₂ valorization technology is the co-electrolysis of water and CO₂ to produce syngas in a ‘Power-to-Syngas’ scenario. This approach aims to replace the current technologies producing ‘grey’ syngas from fossil resources with co-electrolysis to obtain renewable syngas. The advantages of high-temperature co-electrolysis include highly efficient conversion, due to the contribution of the RWGS, low aging rates, the ability to operate in transient modes in response to the fluctuating availability of RE sources [19,20], raw material availability as well as potential synergies from integration with downstream chemical synthesis [21].

Among the various innovative solutions proposed to achieve decarbonization in marine fuel technology, e-MGO produced from water, CO₂, and RE stands out. Fig. 1 illustrates this PtL concept to produce synthetic fuels. Initially, syngas is produced from water and CO₂ using RE through co-electrolysis. Subsequently, the resulting syngas is converted into liquid fuels, specifically e-MGO, via Fischer-Tropsch

synthesis.

As interest in developing marine e-fuels grows, assessing the feasibility of their production in the coming years becomes increasingly crucial. Although several techno-economic studies have evaluated alternative fuels for maritime transport [22–24], they rarely address resource availability in detail. A report by Concawe [25] analyzed the technical potential for RE production in Europe, concluding that the available RE and CO₂ from large point sources in 2030 would be sufficient to meet the anticipated demand for Power-to-Liquid (PtL) production. However, it also highlighted that in the mid- to long-term horizon (2050), the supply from concentrated CO₂ sources might become more constrained [26].

The current literature reveals significant deficiencies in addressing the specific availability of resources for marine e-fuels. Notably, there is a lack of comprehensive studies focusing on the availability of CO₂, water, and RE for these fuels, as well as an insufficient examination of resource availability in particular locations and regions. Furthermore, existing research predominantly focuses on general e-fuels and methanol [27], rather than specifically on marine e-fuels such as e-MGO. This study aims to fill these gaps by providing a detailed assessment of resource availability for producing e-MGO, with a specific focus on the Port of Barcelona (PB) as a representative example of coastal hubs and international ports, offering valuable insights for global applications.

2. Methodology

2.1. Case study

The PB is the third-largest port in Spain by production volume. It has become a reference port for fuel supply in the Mediterranean due to its high level of traffic and competitive capacity [28]. Additionally, the PB, in collaboration with IREC, joined the World Ports Climate Action Program (WPCAP) in July 2018, a global initiative aimed at promoting decarbonization in the port and maritime sectors [29]. A key focus of the program is to support and facilitate the development of new carbon-neutral fuels with very low atmospheric pollutant emissions. Despite EU regulations (based on 1990 levels), the PB has established a more ambitious target in its strategic plan: a 50 % reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to levels from 2017 [30]. The adoption and promotion of new, cleaner alternative fuels for maritime transport is considered a priority line of action, enabling the PB to decarbonize its activities and improve air quality in its surroundings. Several potential mainstream fuels have been identified, including biofuels (such as bio-methane and biodiesel) and synthetic e-fuels (such as ammonia and methanol). In this scenario, the PB has expressed its intention to be one of the first to be prepared to attract actors from the whole supply chain, both by sourcing from foreign producers and by establishing production

Fig. 1. Schematic of the power-to-fuel process with co-electrolysis and Fischer –Tropsch Synthesis.

facilities within the port itself [31].

The demand for MGO at the PB fluctuated significantly, reaching 199 ktons in 2019, dropping to 70 ktons in 2020 due to the impact of COVID-19, and then increasing again to 222 ktons by 2022 (Fig. 1 – SI). This trend indicates a substantial recovery and growth in demand following the notable decline in 2020.

For this case study, a demand of 200 ktons of e-MGO was considered, and the mass balance was performed considering a base of 1 kg of e-MGO. The e-MGO was defined as a mix of hydrocarbons in the range of C₉ to C₂₀ [32].

2.2. Process overview

2.2.1. Co-electrolysis

Steam and CO₂ can be separately transformed on their reduced species (H₂ and CO) and then combined to form syngas. However, significant advantages exist in simultaneously reducing both steam and CO₂ through a co-electrolysis process. Firstly, co-electrolysis is more cost-effective and energy-efficient due to the faster overall electrochemical kinetics [19]. Secondly, a substantial amount of CO₂ is converted to CO during co-electrolysis through the reverse water–gas shift (RWGS) reaction, significantly reducing the total electrical consumption needed to produce syngas [20,33]. Thirdly, the introduction of steam during co-electrolysis effectively suppresses carbon deposition, which is a major issue in dry CO₂ electrolysis due to CO₂ reduction to carbon, leading to severe coking and loss of cell function. Therefore, high-temperature steam/CO₂ co-electrolysis is a highly efficient technology for syngas production, offering lower costs and enhanced durability.

Co-electrolysis can be performed at both high and low temperatures. High-temperature co-electrolysis utilizes Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) technology [19]. Solid-oxide electrolyzers capitalize on the reduced need for electrical power as temperature rise, resulting in a lower power requirement compared to low-temperature electrolysis technologies [34]. The total energy needed for H₂O and CO₂ splitting consists of a fraction of electrical energy (the Gibbs free energy, ΔG_f) and a fraction of heat energy (TΔS_f) as described by eq. (1). [35]. Thus, the electrolyzer's power demand decreases with increasing temperatures.

$$\Delta H_f = \Delta G_f + T\Delta S_f \quad (1)$$

In co-electrolysis mode, H₂O and CO₂ are converted to syngas by the reduction of both species simultaneously. The chemical reactions occurring at the cathode under provision of electrons are shown by Eq. (2) and (3).

The generated oxygen ions are transferred to the anode via the solid electrolyte, where they are oxidized to gaseous O₂, as shown in Eq. (4) [34]

Due to the high operating temperatures (800–900 °C) and the presence of catalytic species, such as Ni, the RWGS (Eq (5)) occurs in parallel to the redox reactions already defined.

When examining the thermal energy involved in the process of electrolysis, special attention is given to the internal thermal losses due to their ability to contribute to the heat required for the reaction. The scenario where these thermal losses align perfectly with the heat needed for the reaction is known as the thermoneutral operating point or thermoneutral voltage (E_{th}). The voltage applied to the SOEC in this situation is termed as the thermoneutral voltage and the efficiency of co-

electrolysis could reach 100 %. However, SOECs are not usually operated exactly at this point, so heat must be supplied when operating at voltages below the E_{th} (endothermal mode) or removed, when operating at higher voltages than E_{th} (exothermal mode). In addition, the overall system efficiency is affected by other factors, such as the energy required for product compression and the voltage conversion losses when rectifying alternating current. Therefore, the overall system efficiency (η_{SOEC}) is defined as the calorific value of the product divided for the input energy (electrical – E_{el,total} and thermal energy – E_{th,total}) as shown in Eq. (6) [36].

$$\eta_{SOEC} = \frac{\sum_i m_i \times LHV_i}{E_{el,total} + E_{th,total}} \quad (6)$$

SOEC systems have already reached a commercial state at the Megawatt scale, with installations above 2.7 MW [37], composed of integrated modules of SOEC stacks of 250 kW. These systems report a conversion efficiency of 82 % (LHV to AC) and aim to achieve efficiencies of 84 % and 86 % by 2025 and 2030, respectively [38]. In a previous work, efficiencies up to 85 %_{LHV} for syngas production have been reported in a system consuming 120 kW_{AC} [39]. In addition, the MegaSyn project is currently underway, aiming to demonstrate the large-scale industrial production of syngas via co-electrolysis of CO₂ and H₂O [40]. Regarding the land requirement for this kind of project, the average space requirement of the last development (2.89 MW) comprising all auxiliary systems is 300 m² [37].

Co-electrolysis processes can be performed with any inlet composition of CO₂ and H₂O mixtures. By adjusting the initial composition of the mixture and monitoring the role of the RWGS reaction, the outlet composition and the H₂/CO ratio can be effectively controlled [41,42]. Typical H₂/CO molar ratios used for integrating co-electrolysis in e-fuel production range from 1 to 3. The parameters considered for the co-electrolysis are shown in Table 1.

2.2.2. Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis

FTS is a process in which syngas is transformed into liquid fuel through catalytic CO hydrogenation and polymerization [44], resulting in a wide range of hydrocarbon chains of different lengths [36]. The primary products of FTS are linear paraffins and water, as shown in Eq. (7)

The Low Temperature Fischer-Tropsch (LTFT) process typically operates with either Fe or Co catalysts at temperatures of 200–260 °C to produce heavy cuts such as wax and diesel [45]. LTFT involves the use of low-temperature Co catalysts-based processes in either Slurry Phase Reactor or multitubular Fixed Bed Reactor [46].

The main goal of LTFT is optimizing long-chain hydrocarbon products for obtaining liquid fuels (e.g. diesel) after synthetic crude refining [47]. Among the best-performing FTS reported to date, an 80 % CO conversion rate and up to 68 % diesel selectivity were reported in a two-stage multi-tubular reactor [48]. The products of the FTS are gases (C₁–C₄), liquids and waxes (C₅₊). The liquid products were categorized as e-gasoline (C₅–C₈), e-MGO (C₉–C₂₀) and e-wax (C₂₁₊). The selectivity of the products was defined based on experimental results of LTFT using a

Table 1
Co-electrolysis process parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value	Ref
Temperature	°C	850	[39]
Pressure	bar	1	[37]
System electrical efficiency	%	82.0 %	[37]
Stack electricity consumption	%	82.3 %	[37]
H ₂ O electrolysis reaction Conversion rate	%	80 %	[43]
CO ₂ electrolysis reaction Conversion rate	%	80 %	[43]
Cell voltage	V	1.224	[35]

Co-based catalyst with lanthanide promotion tested under a stream of syngas containing a 32 % of CO₂ [49]. These specific conditions are more representative for the coupling of FTS units to CO₂-to- syngas processes (such as co-electrolysis) that do not attain 100 % CO₂ conversion. It is also important to highlight that, although the selectivity for the desired product (e-MGO) is 54 %, other products such as e-gasoline, e-wax, and tail gas are also valuable and can be utilized in additional processes. A summary of the operating conditions and selectivity of products considered for the FTS unit in this study, is detailed in Table 2.

2.2.3. Process design

The detailed process to obtain e-MGO via coupling of co-electrolysis and FTS is shown in Fig. 2. The inlet water stream is mixed with water recycle from the condenser before further processing in the steam generator. CO₂ and steam are mixed and heated to 850 °C before entering to the cathode of the SOEC unit. Part of the required heat is supplied by the outlet gases, while the remaining portion is provided by the necessary electrical energy.

On the anode side, sweep air is compressed to 2 bar and heated to the SOEC operating temperature before being fed into the system. Sweep air is mainly used to help flushing the oxygen produced in the porous structure of the electrode. It also helps controlling the temperature of the stack and the pressure difference across the cell (from both sides of the electrolyte). The sweep air is introduced at a rate that results in an anode effluent with a molar fraction of 50 % O₂ [50]. The SOEC converts steam and CO₂ into a syngas rich stream which exits from the cathode. The syngas is cooled first to 100 °C, to separate the water, and thereafter it is cooled to 25 °C before compression.

An important aspect of the integration of SOEC and FTS units is syngas compression, which is sometimes overlooked in process design. Syngas exits the SOEC unit at atmospheric pressure and must be compressed to the FTS pressure (20 bar). Effective compression is crucial for optimizing the efficiency and performance of the overall process. The syngas is compressed to the FTS reactor's pressure level via a three-stage compression step with intermediate cooling. After compression, the syngas is mixed with tail gas recirculation and heated to the FTS operating temperature of 230 °C. In the FTS reactor, part of syngas is converted into gases and liquid hydrocarbons. The separation of FTS condensate products (e-wax, e-MGO, e- gasoline and water) is carried out by three heat exchangers using cooling water. Subsequently, a share of the tail gas stream is recirculated to the entrance of the FTS reactor, whereas the remaining tail gas leaves the system as purge gas.

The recirculation of tail gas allows increasing the overall conversion of carbon monoxide (CO), thereby enhancing the synthesis of products and improving the Power-to-Liquid efficiency. To prevent the accumulation of CO₂ and CH₄ in the recirculated tail gas, a portion of the stream must be purged from the system. The recirculation ratio (RR) is defined as the mass flow rate of recirculated tail gas divided by the total mass

flow rate of tail gas as shown in Eq. (8) [13]. The tail gas recirculation was adjusted to 90 % to maximize recirculation without requiring external heat. The recirculated syngas is re-pressurized before being mixed with the SOEC syngas.

$$RR = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{tail gas, rec}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{tail gas, total}}} \quad (8)$$

To design the process, the system efficiency was evaluated considering two key performance indicators (KPIs): Power-to-liquid efficiency (η_{PIL}) and carbon efficiency (η_{Carbon}).

The Power-to-Liquid efficiency is defined as the chemical energy stored in the liquid products divided by the total energy inputs. In this case, the total energy input is equal to the system's total electric power input [13]

$$\eta_{\text{PIL}} = \frac{\sum_j \dot{m}_j \cdot \text{LHV}_j}{P_{\text{el, total}}}, j = [\text{naphta, diesel, wax}] \quad (9)$$

Carbon efficiency is defined as the ratio of carbon atoms being transformed into the process and the number of carbons inserted to the PtL plant [34].

$$\eta_{\text{carbon}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{Carbon, in}} - \dot{n}_{\text{Carbon, out}}}{\dot{n}_{\text{Carbon, in}}} \quad (10)$$

2.3. Available supply of resources

The scope of the region evaluated for each resource was determined based on the location of the case study, the geopolitical administration of the resource, and the available information. For this case study at the PB, RE data is reported for the region of Catalonia, and water resources are considered within the context of the metropolitan area of Barcelona. In the case of biogenic CO₂, due to the lack of precise information of the Catalonia region, and the reliance on estimations, the scope of the study was extended to Spain.

To evaluate the available resources, we first identified and assessed the maximum supply of these resources. Since not all the maximum supply can be utilized due to various factors, we then evaluated the accessible supply. This accessible supply represents the resources that are available for use. For the present scenario, we used the latest available data, and for future scenarios, we considered estimations and projections. Finally, we compared the resource requirements with the available resources.

2.3.1. Renewable energy

RE availability consider the energy generated from wind (eolic), photovoltaic, hydropower, renewable cogeneration, biogas, solar thermal, municipal solid waste and agricultural and forest biomass [51].

RE generation was considered for both the present and potential future scenarios in the region of Catalonia. The RE requirement was then calculated by dividing the RE needed for the system to produce e-MGO in one year by the total amount of RE generated in Catalonia during the same period, as shown in Eq. (11).

$$\%RE \text{ requirement} = \frac{RE \text{ required (TWh)}}{RE \text{ accessible (TWh)}} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

2.3.2. Biogenic CO₂

The RED Delegated Act for greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) for RFNBOs, proposes to restrict the types of CO₂ that can be used for fuel production, particularly after 2041 [52]. It means that from 2041 only CO₂ from biogenic sources, direct air capture, or some geologic CO₂ would be allowed [53].

For the biogenic CO₂ in Spain, the sources considered were typical industries (paper, waste management, cement, chemicals, and food and drinks), and power generation from biomass [53–55]. The maximum

Table 2
Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis operating conditions.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
Temperature	T _{FT}	°C	230
Pressure	P _{FT}	Bar	20
Ratio H ₂ /CO feed FT	H ₂ /CO	mol H ₂ /mol CO	2.1
CO conversion (1 step)	X _{CO}	%	55 %
H ₂ conversion	X _{H2}	%	55 %
CO ₂ conversion	X _{CO2}	%	15 %
Selectivity			
Gases			
	C ₁	%	9 %
	C ₂ -C ₄	%	4 %
Liquids			
e-Gasoline	C ₅ -C ₈	%	87 %
e-MGO	C ₉ -C ₂₀	%	20 %
e-Wax	C ₂₁ +	%	54 %
			13 %

Fig. 2. Scheme of the Power-to-Liquid plant.

supply of biogenic CO₂ emissions was calculated by two ways. For typical industries, it is based on the estimations reported by ERM [53]. In the case of developing industries such as biomethane and bioethanol, biogenic CO₂ was calculated from their current production and a known biogenic CO₂ production factor (2 t CO₂/ t biomethane produced and 0.56 t CO₂/ t bioethanol produced) [53].

The accessible biogenic CO₂ was calculated applying a screening process. This screening process is carried out because not all the maximum biogenic emissions will be available for capture and utilization. It considers internal factors, such as the scale of the emitter, CO₂ concentration within flue gases, and potential capture rate, as well as external factors, such as the location of the emitters and proximity to pipeline infrastructure for the collection of CO₂. The factors considered are presented in the SI.

To estimate future biogenic CO₂ emissions, the analysis considered only the projected growth of the biomethane industry in Spain, while the other CO₂ sources were considered to remain constant. The estimation of biogenic CO₂ emissions was based on biomethane production projections reported by the European Biogas Association [56].

The CO₂ requirement is calculated by dividing the CO₂ required for the system to produce e-MGO in one year by the total amount of accessible biogenic CO₂ in Spain during the same period as shown in Eq. (12).

$$\%CO_2 \text{ requirement} = \frac{CO_2 \text{ required (Mtonnes)}}{CO_2 \text{ accessible (Mtonnes)}} \times 100 \quad (12)$$

2.3.3. Water

Water consumption is becoming a critical topic in the life cycle assessment of alternative fuels due to its significant effects on human health and ecosystems [57]. The metropolitan area of Barcelona, characterized by its location on the west mediterranean coast, high density of population and important industrial activity, consumes more water than the environment and surrounding infrastructures can naturally provide [58]. In this context, analyzing the water requirements of the proposed Power-to-Liquid plant becomes even more relevant.

The water sources include conventional resources, such as water from rivers and aquifers [58], or unconventional water resources, such as reused water and desalination, which were taken from the Strategic Plan of the integral cycle of the water in the Metropolitan area of Barcelona [59]. The estimation of the future scenario considers a reduction of surface and underground water resources by 12 % and 9 %, respectively [58].

The maximum supply of water refers to the total amount of water available from these sources. The accessible supply of water is considered as the profitable water, which is the amount of water that could be used if all the necessary infrastructure were available [58].

The water requirement is calculated by dividing the water required for the system to produce e-MGO in one year by the total amount of accessible water in the metropolitan Area of Barcelona during the same period as shown in Eq. (13).

$$\%Water \text{ requirement} = \frac{Water \text{ required (hm}^3\text{)}}{Water \text{ accessible (hm}^3\text{)}} \times 100 \quad (13)$$

3. Results

3.1. Resources requirement and system energy balance

To evaluate the system's performance, the initial analysis focuses on identifying the resource requirements for producing 1 kg of e-MGO and assessing the associated energy consumption. Fig. 3 presents the material balance of the system, which includes co-electrolysis, FTS, and a product separation process to produce 1 kg of e-MGO from CO₂, water, and electricity. The system assumes a tail gas recirculation ratio (RR) of 90 %. The resources required to produce 1 kg of e-MGO are: 33.8 kWh of electricity, 6.7 kg of CO₂ and 2.0 kg of water. The detailed mass and energy balance can be found in Table S2.

A total of 5.7 kg of water per kg of e-MGO produced is required as feed for the co-electrolysis process. However, by reusing condensed water separated from the syngas exiting the SOEC, the requirement for fresh water would be 4.6 kg. Additionally, considering the use of water produced from the FTS process (2.6 kg), the net water requirement is 2.0 kg per kg of e-MGO produced. The co-electrolysis process produces 5.3 kg of syngas, consisting of 62.7 % hydrogen, 29.9 % carbon monoxide, and 7.5 % CO₂. Additionally, the total process yields 0.38 kg of e-gasoline, 0.25 kg of e-wax, and 1.05 kg of tail gas along with the e-MGO. It is important to note that, although this study focuses on e-MGO production, the other products of the FTS process are sustainable hydrocarbons than can be directly used as fuels (tail gas, e-gasoline) or after post-treatment (e-wax).

Fig. 4 shows the energy distribution within the process when 100 MJ of electricity is supplied as alternating current (AC). The total electricity demand considered includes all electrical and heating equipment in the system. It is evident that the SOEC unit is the primary consumer of

Fig. 3. Resources requirement to produce 1 kg of e-MGO from CO₂, H₂O and electricity using a combined SOEC-FTS technology.

Fig. 4. System energy balance for 100 MJ of input electricity.

electricity, accounting for 79.5 % of the input. Nearly 100 % of the input electricity in the SOEC unit is converted to syngas. In the FTS, syngas energy is converted into various products: tail gas, e-gasoline, e-MGO, and e-wax, with the remaining heat being released. As shown, approximately 43 % of the syngas energy is converted into e-MGO.

The Power-to-Liquid efficiency, accounting to produce e-gasoline, e-MGO, and e-wax, was found to be 56.0 %. This is slightly higher than previous similar studies, such as the work by Pratschner et al., which reported an efficiency of 50.8 % [13]. The difference can be attributed to

two factors: firstly, the relatively high selectivity for e-MGO (54 %), and secondly, the slightly higher SOEC efficiency considered in our study (82 % compared to 80 %). Additionally, the overall plant efficiency, including the purge gas produced, was 71.4 %. At the light of the obtained plant efficiency, e-MGO produced via co-SOEC appears to be a viable alternative. However, the availability of electricity for scaling up this process should be estimated.

3.2. Electricity requirement

In 2022, the RE generated in Catalonia was 6.9 TWh, representing 15.6 % of the total generation. Nuclear energy was the main source of electric power generation, accounting for 56.2 % of the total production. Additionally, hydroelectric and wind energy were the main RE sources for producing electrical energy, representing 6.8 % and 5.8 % of the total generation, respectively. According to the Energy Perspective of Catalonia 2050, the RE generation is projected to reach 35.1 TWh by 2030 and 115.9 TWh by 2050, with significant contributions expected from wind (eolic) and photovoltaic sources [60].

Fig. 5 illustrates the RE generated in Catalonia in 2022 [61], along with projections for 2030 and 2050 [60]. It also compares the %RE requirement for e-MGO substitution at the PB. The total electricity needed to meet the annual MGO demand of the PB (200,000 tonnes) is 6.7 TWh. This amount would be equivalent to 97.5 % of the total RE generated in Catalonia in 2022, indicating that currently, it would not be feasible to replace all fossil based MGO with e-MGO at the PB. However, considering the projections for RE generation in Catalonia for 2030 and 2050, this value would decrease to 19.3 % and 5.8 %, respectively, assuming that MGO demand remains constant.

3.3. CO₂ requirement

Producing 1.0 kg of e-MGO requires 6.7 kg of CO₂, as detailed in Section 3.1. Fig. 6 illustrates the estimated accessible biogenic CO₂ in Spain for current and future scenarios and the %CO₂ requirement for e-MGO substitution at the PB. In 2020, the biogenic CO₂ required (1.34 Mt CO₂/year) would be equivalent to 76.0 % of the total available supply, representing a significant amount when compared to the country's total. For 2030 and 2050, there is a noticeable increase in accessible biogenic CO₂ due to the projected growth of the biogas and biomethane industries. By 2030, the biogenic CO₂ demand would represent one-third of the accessible biogenic CO₂ in Spain, and by 2050, this demand would be 9.0 %.

3.4. Water requirement

The total annual water requirement for producing 200 ktonnes of e-MGO at the PB is 0.404 hm³ per year. Fig. 7 illustrates the water availability in the metropolitan area of Barcelona during drought conditions, both in the present and in a future (2050) scenario. It also shows the percentage of water required for e-MGO production at the PB. In the present scenario, this water requirement represents 0.084 % of the

Fig. 5. RE availability in the region in present and future scenarios and requirement of the PB to produce e-MGO.

Fig. 6. Biogenic CO₂ availability in Spain in present and future scenarios and requirement of the PB to produce e-MGO.

Fig. 7. Water availability (drought scenario) in the region in present and future scenarios and water requirement to produce e-MGO in the PB.

available water in the metropolitan area of Barcelona, while in the future scenario, it increases slightly to 0.090 %. These findings suggest that the water needed for e-MGO production at the PB is minimal when compared to the total water availability from various sources in the region.

Additionally, a comparison of the water requirements with the treatment capacities of the Llobregat regeneration and desalination plants—two potential water sources due to their proximity and origin—shows that these requirements account for 0.17 % and 0.37 % of the capacities, respectively. These results indicate that the water demand is very low compared to the treatment capacities.

4. Discussion

The present work highlights the importance of designing a sustainable process by considering both current and projected resources, along with the technologies involved. This study evaluates, firstly, high energy efficiency technologies and, additionally, methods such as tail gas recirculation and the reuse of materials, including water from co-electrolysis and FTS, to ensure the viability and sustainability of the proposed route. A total system efficiency of 56.4 % was estimated, assuming 90 % tail gas recirculation. Meeting the current MGO demand at the PB would require 6.7 TWh/year of electricity, 1.34 million tonnes

of CO₂ annually, and 0.404 m³ of water per year.

Table 3 summarizes the percentage of resource requirements for replacing fossil-based MGO at the PB by the equivalent e-MGO. It was found out that currently, 98 % of the RE generated in Catalonia and 76 % of the biogenic CO₂ available in Spain would be needed for this substitution. These values indicate that, under current conditions, replacing MGO is not feasible, as the available resources are insufficient to fully meet the demand for e-MGO. However, future projections suggest that by 2030, these requirements will decrease to 19 % for RE and 33 % for biogenic CO₂, and further to 6 % and 9 % by 2050, respectively, demonstrating that as resource availability increases, the feasibility of replacing fossil-based MGO with e-MGO will significantly improve.

Despite the projections for RE generation in Catalonia, the data reported for 2023 indicate that RE accounted for only 15.7 % of the region's total energy production [62]. Additionally, the installed capacity in 2023 [63] shows that wind power represents 22 % of the target for 2030 [60], while solar photovoltaic accounts for just 4.3 % of the projected capacity for the same year. These figures highlight the significant progress still required in the deployment of these technologies to meet the future goals. In terms of RE, it is important to note that currently 11.5 % of Spain's primary energy consumption is allocated to MGO for maritime transport [66]. By comparison, the estimated 6 % of RE required to produce e-MGO by 2050 would be significantly lower, suggesting that replacing fossil-based MGO with e-MGO will be feasible as resource availability improves.

Regarding CO₂, this work demonstrates that there is currently insufficient biogenic CO₂ to fully replace MGO. However, biogenic CO₂ availability could increase in the future with the development of other sectors. A key factor in this potential increase is the development of carbon capture projects, as well as the growth of emerging industries. Sectors such as biomethane, bio-syngas, biorefineries and waste management are expected to play a significant role in supplying biogenic CO₂. In this context, the CO₂SMOS project aims to digitally locate facilities generating biogenic CO₂, helping stakeholders to establish synergies [55].

The PB is exploring nearby sources of biogenic CO₂ and assessing the feasibility of constructing CO₂ pipelines to connect these sources. One potential source under consideration is a biomethane plant that may be implemented at the port. Additionally, the PB is collaborating with IREC on the SUPORT project, which aims to revalorize CO₂ by converting it into renewable fuels for maritime transport, such as e-MGO [64].

The water requirement for the SOEC-FT system do not impose a significant strain on the water production capacity of the Barcelona metropolitan area. However, in scenarios of water scarcity, it is crucial to consider unconventional water sources, such as desalinated and regenerated water. Desalinated water is an attractive option because its source, seawater, is virtually unlimited. Nevertheless, the main disadvantage of desalination is its high treatment cost. Conversely, regenerated water is currently underutilized. Nowadays, it is not typically used for potable water production due to regulatory and public perception challenges [58]. Cost comparisons show that desalinated water costs approximately 0.64 €/m³, whereas reclaimed water costs about 0.13 €/m³ [65]. This significant cost difference underscores the economic advantage of using reclaimed water over desalinated water as an

Table 3

Summary of the percentage of resource requirements to replace fossil MGO in the PB.

Resource	Reference	Current ^a	2030	2050
Renewable energy	Catalonia	98 %	19 %	6 %
Biogenic CO ₂	Spain	76 %	33 %	9 %
Water	Metropolitan Area of Barcelona	0.08 %	0.08 %	0.09 %

^a Renewable energy (2022), Biogenic CO₂ and H₂O (2020).

alternative in the SOEC-FT system.

The results presented are influenced by limitations in the data sources. CO₂ estimations are affected by 1) the limited availability of biogenic CO₂ data in Spain, requiring estimates based on other countries; 2) the margin of error in carbon capture percentages, which varies by technology and process scale; and 3) projections based solely on contributions from the biogas industry and biomethane projects, excluding other sectors. Additionally, the projected values for RE generation depend on the completion of planned installations. For water availability, projections assume the use of regenerated water to maintain aquifer levels; any failures in regeneration could significantly impact future water supply [58].

To assess the potential impact of not meeting optimistic projections, we conducted a sensitivity analysis focusing on the two most scarce resources: RE and biogenic CO₂. The results of this analysis are presented in Tables S3 and S4. In a scenario where 50 % of the projected RE generation for 2050 is achieved, the electricity requirement would account for 12 % of the total RE generated, indicating that full replacement of MGO would still be possible. Furthermore, this percentage aligns with the current share of primary energy dedicated to the maritime sector in Spain. In a similar way, if only 50 % of the estimated biogenic CO₂ is available by 2050, the CO₂ requirement for replacing the MGO for e-MGO at the PB would represent 18 % of the total biogenic CO₂ available, which still indicates feasibility. It is important to note that, while projections for RE are more diversified and reliable, those for CO₂ are contingent on the successful growth of the biogas and biomethane market in Spain [66]. Thus, one of the key findings of this work is that the market for e-fuels is closely linked to the development of the biomethane sector.

Finally, an important aspect to consider is that, despite the consideration of the total replacement of MGO proposed in this study, the targets for the introduction of RFNBOs will be implemented gradually. The European Parliament plenary's final position on RED III included an RFNBO target of 1.2 % in maritime transport starting in 2030 [53,67]. Since e-MGO has the capacity to be used as a drop-in fuel, it is expected to be integrated as a blend with MGO [68]. In these scenarios where lower demand is considered, resource availability may not be a limiting factor.

5. Conclusions

This study concludes that e-MGO represents a promising and viable alternative for future energy scenarios, provided the necessary resources are expected to be available for its implementation by 2050. However, site-specific studies are crucial to evaluate resource availability at each location. For instance, for the complete replacement of fossil-derived MGO with e-MGO at the Port of Barcelona by 2050, the RE required for e-MGO production would account for 6 % of the region's total supply, the biogenic CO₂ demand would constitute 9 % of the expected availability in Spain, and the water requirement would represent just 0.09 % of the supply for the metropolitan area of Barcelona.

Additionally, overcoming resource constraints in adopting synthetic fuels for maritime transport will require the expansion of RE generation and the development of the biomethane industry. Nevertheless, as e-MGO will be gradually integrated into the energy mix, resource availability is not expected to pose significant limitations to its implementation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karen Quintana: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Andrés A. García Blanco:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lucile Bernadet:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Daniel Ruiz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Marc Torrell:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding

acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jordi Guilera:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2024.100800>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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